

Academic Quality - Some Thoughts

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Synopsis

This brief report summarizes my thoughts following discussions during the Spring 2022 term. It is composed as a rather phenomenological exposé for the record. As such, its use is most suitable as a source of background information, preliminary to a proceeding rigorous study. The views promoted below would appear to be somewhat biased towards a quality definition as it applies more suitably to a *Liberal Arts and Sciences* university, rather than a *Neo-Liberal Corporate* university. The bias may be felt also in the lopsidedness of the references mentioned. I look forward to a wider discussion, where contrary ideas pertinent to other types of universities may also be presented.

1 Quality and Academic Quality

The Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines the adjective “quality” to refer to “high quality”, i.e., having a large degree of “quality”. As a noun, the dictionary provides several entries. Of those, we list the ones that are most relevant to academic quality.

1	Nature, Property	peculiar and essential character, e.g., “a disturbing quality of on-line education”
2	Characteristic, Timber, Vividness	distinguishing attribute, e.g., “the tonal quality contributed to the overall success of the band”
3	Grade, Rank	degree of excellence, superiority in kind, e.g., “the quality of the cafeteria food was a determining factor”

An initial source of confusion and miscommunication during discussions was due to the various different definitions of “quality”. At the simplest level, do we speak of “characteristics” or of “rank”? That is, are we focused more on “what attributes are appropriate for education” or “the level of our excellence”? Moreover, if the latter, to what do we compare our level? Is it our past performance, or that of other institutions? Given that there are different determinants of “excellence” and that no single institution is a non-dominated superior in all such factors, which factors do we prioritize, and why? Presumably, the “why” must be related back to the national and regional needs, which in itself is a demanding task.

The confusion is highlighted in an OECD study¹ regarding teaching quality.

But quality teaching lacks a clear definition, because quality can be regarded as an outcome or a property, or even a process, and because conceptions of teaching quality happen to be stakeholder relative.

¹The Path to Quality Teaching in Higher Education, F. Henard and S. Leprince-Ringuet.

At the onset, we must also note that there are interrelated concepts, often associated and sometimes confused with quality, such as *faculty performance* or *student achievement*.

As we contemplate “academic quality”, we are mindful of existing literature. Typically, the literature classifies quality² issues under a few domains.

- Course design, development, and deployment
- Course resources (laboratories, library, etc.)
- Faculty competency and well-being
- Student support
- Institutional and administrative support
- Evaluation and assessment

This is by no means an exhaustive set, but rather what had emerged from limited discussions. Nonetheless, these aspects are useful in developing an operational definition of the concept.

Moreover, the flurry of activity during the past few decades has led to the notion of the “quality culture”. As it applies to higher education, much have been debated as to how and why such a culture must be established, and what factors have positive or negative effects on such an institutional culture of quality. A good summary is from Bendermacher et al.³. Further radicalized of the notion of “quality culture” is also present. For instance, DeMarco and Lister use the term the “cult of quality”⁴.

²Referring to “academic quality”, we simply use the word “quality” and omit the word “academic” when it is implied.

³Unraveling quality culture in higher education: a realist review, Bendermacher et al., High Educ (2017) 73:39–60 DOI 10.1007/s10734-015-9979-2.

⁴Peopleware: Productive Projects and Teams DeMarco and Lister, Dorset House Pub., 1999.

Table 1 Promoting and inhibiting organisational context factors impacting quality culture

Promoting elements	Inhibiting elements
<i>Organisational structure/managerial elements</i>	
Strategy of continuous improvement	Hierarchical structure/structural division
Quality management systems	Lack of staff and student involvement in organisational decision making
Staff and student involvement in organisational decision making	Neglect of evolving student demands
Taking into account evolving student demands	Lack of policies, procedures, systems, responsibilities
Clear policies, procedures, systems responsibilities	Lack of resources
	Top-down (managerial) approaches to quality management implementation
	Research focus
<i>Organisational subculture/psychological elements</i>	
Flexible, people-oriented cultures	Rigid, control-oriented cultures
Presence of various cultures	Presence of strong disciplinary cultures
Shared (educational) quality values	Research culture/undervaluing education
<i>Leadership elements</i>	
Leadership commitment and skills	Lack of leadership commitment and skills
Allocate resources	Focus on inspection and control
Create partnerships, influence people management	Acting as communication gatekeepers
Create climate of trust and shared understanding	
Ability to perform multiple roles	
Setting and communicating policies	
<i>Communication elements</i>	
Communication/information for quality	Lacking communication/information for quality
Provide information on strategies and policies	Lack of sharing best practices across the organisation
Clear tasks requirements and responsibilities	Lack of appropriate communication channels

Figure 1: Quality Culture

Taken from “Unraveling quality culture in higher education: a realist review, Bendermacher et al., 2017”.

An immediate derivative of the notion promoted by Bendermacher et al. is that the quality culture benefits from a more liberal and inclusive environment compared to a more rigid control oriented one.

2 A Definition of “Academic Quality”

There may be a myriad of definitions of academic quality. Of the few definitions entertained, the one most discussed at SITE is best represented by the definition from the University of Glasgow. The University of Glasgow⁵ defines academic quality as

⁵Academic Quality Framework, University of Glasgow, November 2021

Academic quality is a way of describing how well the learning opportunities available to students help them to achieve their award. It is about making sure that appropriate and effective teaching, support, assessment and learning opportunities are provided for them.

This definition proposes that the academic environment is responsible for the establishment of favorable conditions for learning. The onus of learning is on the students. If some students succeed in learning then the academic environment should be declared as being of sufficient quality. An immediate corollary of this definition is that any measurement of quality is not contingent on the success of all students. It is entirely possible that the institution is of sufficient quality (i.e., is providing a fertile environment for learning) but the students do not learn. After all, the student has the legal right to take a class and fail if she so desires⁶.

This notion is often openly declared, for instance, as illustrated by the Atlanta Metropolitan State College website⁷, which gives students advise on academic success.

Remember that you alone are responsible for your academic achievement. Your instructor is your guide and your classmates may help you to understand your assignments; however, you are responsible for your own success.

Some posit that quality improvement starts with the students. This notion has even prompted discussion on how to empower students as agents of change⁸.

3 Indicators of “Academic Quality”

Academic quality is almost always measured by a set of performance measures or indicators. These are typically quantitative measures, whose values are easily treated as statistics. One could perform many arithmetic operations, such as computing averages, standard deviations, ranges, modes, medians, etc. The numerics also allow for the values to be compared to past performances to extract trends and set flags when thresholds are breached.

On the more general survey regarding the factors that influence academic excellence, a pre-pandemic study finds factors scrutinized in the literature to be poor indicators⁹.

⁶The etymology of the Azerbaijani word “talaba” is related to “desire” or “demand”. This term presupposes that the student is desirous of learning, and has no intention to exercise her right to fail.

⁷See <https://www.atlm.edu/academics/keys-to-academic-success.aspx>

⁸“Rethinking the values of higher education - students as change agents?” , J. Kay, E. Dunne and J. Hutchinson, Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education, 2010.

⁹See “Review of the research literature on defining and demonstrating quality teaching and impact in higher education, 2016”, available on line.

Mapping of indicators used in the literature to operationalise 'quality teaching'			
Quality teaching level	Indicators found in the literature review	Quality of evidence in literature for use of indicator ¹	
Student experience	Social experience and development	Weak	
	Degree and quality of participation	Weak	
	Extent to which students feel challenged	Weak	
Teacher performance	Competence and expertise	Medium	
	Formal qualifications	Weak	
	Ability to inspire and engage	Weak	
	Respect and care for students	Medium	
	Contribution to their profession (innovation)	Weak	
	Teaching methods	Weak	
	Self-monitoring	Weak	
	Curriculum design	Weak	
	Usefulness of subject matter	Weak	
	Availability to students	Medium	
	Institution	Administrative and financial management	Weak
		Funding and facilities	Medium
Teaching facilities		Medium	
Well adapted learning environments		Weak	
Availability of and equal access to student guidance and support services		Weak	
Equitable treatment of faculties		Weak	
Availability of teaching training		Weak	
Community involvement		Weak	
Employer engagement		Weak	
Communication with staff and students		Medium	
Extra-curricular activities		Medium	
Rewards for quality teaching		Weak	

Figure 2: Indicators of “quality teaching”

Taken from “Review of the research literature on defining and demonstrating quality teaching and impact in higher education, Strang et al., In partnership with RAND Europe”.

Most indicators seem to be weak in their predictive power. Only a few seem to have a moderate value in determining and assessing teaching quality. This is quite troublesome, as quality is often quantified and measured so that its improvement could be tracked and reported.

4 The Changing Landscape of Higher Education

One must also be mindful of the changes in higher education. These are affected by technological developments as well as social and political processes.

The universities and professors are no longer seen as the only reservoir of information. One can learn from many sources. A response to this fact has manifested itself in the concept of the *flipped classroom*. However, it could be argued that the ample availability of knowledge outside the university would have to be addressed by more substantial modalities than a simple flipping.

If students do not come to the university for knowledge, then what exactly is the attrac-

tor? One could list a few reasons. Below is an incomplete list.

- Social skills
- Future professional networking
- Facilities, e.g., laboratories
- Team work, interdisciplinary work
- Belonging to an exclusive society
- A diploma
- Access to industry/professional institutions
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If indeed the function of the university is in flux, then so must the approach to academic quality. In fact, one could argue that the determination of the specific function or functions of the university is a prerequisite for the way academic quality matters are to be structured.

Moreover, the said functions may differ from school to school. In Engineering, laboratories may be at the top of the list, while at International Relations, it may be networking or access to supra-national institutions. The fragmentation of the principal function would inevitably lead to the diversification and dispersion of downstream forms.

5 Concluding Remarks

It seems that the same concerns that made TQM, ISO 9000, Lean manufacturing, and Six Sigma fashionable in the 80s and 90s are still relevant. Defining and improving “quality”, whatever that may entail for the specific institution, is a good place to start the soul-searching effort towards institutional identity, character, culture, purpose, and effectiveness. In this respect, we may benefit from intensive and continuous discussions on the subject matter. This brief report leaves much to be desired. At the least, we should question whether *quality* could be measured by *quantitative* indicators. Those yet-to-be-discussed issues notwithstanding, the report is submitted in hopes of serving as a catalyst.